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“SEVEN MINUTES AND HOPEFULLY MORE”

14th of February, I need to hurry, Doctors are calling here and there for I am a hospice nurse, who cares for terminally ill patients near the end of their life. You know, helping them die as comfortably as they can be.

Like many of those who are working in a hospital, I have seen a lot of deaths, untimely deaths, husband's death, wife's death, and all of which that you can think of. While contemplating and noticing loved songs on the air, I wonder how one of the many patients I had, enjoyed looking like smiling despite of being declared dead by the physician.

“I am so sorry Juanita, your husband has irreversible cessation of circulatory and respiratory functions,” “but wait Doc., what do you mean?”, “He is dead, nurses please facilitate.” As a hospice nurse, I came so surprised when the declared dead named Alfie who is still consciously smiling-looking and as I go over with my watch, it's seven o'clock in the evening. Rebecca comes, the wife, I dare to ask, “Maam, look at your husband's gentle face, maybe he is truly ready for this. The wife can't still accept the fact and voluntarily shared their love at first sight story of which all I learned that it all had started at a nearby store of whom there is a vending tempura. “Maam, I couldn't accept it, he has been my rock, God, please revived!”, “Who could love me the way he did? “The funniest things we love to do, simple things that we can no longer do.” And sobbing... “I did understand her story. I absorbed completely well, that made me teary-eyed too. As I imagine, maybe that's what his late husband thought to. “Oh, Ma'am I have to get inside to finish my work,” and “as I looked at my watch, it's already seven o'clock in the evening and seven minutes. I am wasting time, but wait, the late husband turned totally pale with some tears falling dry and so unmoving. “Hay, at least I can now leave myself unshaking, he must really be dead!”

As I go out, I advised the wife that maybe with our seven minutes conversation equated her husband's seven minutes emerging memories while still alive and full of life with her, so intertwining, what a surreal manner. The wife replied, “I cannot believe that even in his last breath, he still weaved our past fragments, reliving our significant memories even it's just seven minutes!”

I ended our conversation with, life is indeed so ironic, the tapestry of their love story comes with a unique blast that even me can't help comfortably extend the minutes left just to retrieve, but hopefully more, there's more in seven minutes with physical touch, but God's appointed time is what we trust.